

Residual balanced attention network for real-time traffic scene semantic segmentation

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ABSTRACT

Intelligent transportation systems (ITS) are among the most focused research in this century. Actually, autonomous driving provides very advanced tasks in terms of road safety monitoring which include identifying dangers on the road and protecting pedestrians. In the last few years, deep learning (DL) approaches and especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been extensively used to solve ITS problems such as traffic scene semantic segmentation and traffic signs classification. Semantic segmentation is an important task that has been addressed in computer vision (CV). Indeed, traffic scene semantic segmentation using CNNs requires high precision with few computational resources to perceive and segment the scene in real-time. However, we often find related work focusing only on one aspect, the precision, or the number of computational parameters. In this regard, we propose RBANet, a robust and lightweight CNN which uses a new proposed balanced attention module, and a new proposed residual module. Afterward, we have simulated our proposed RBANet using three loss functions to get the best combination using only 0.74M parameters. The RBANet has been evaluated on CamVid, the most used dataset in semantic segmentation, and it has performed well in terms of parameters' requirements and precision compared to related work.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Intelligent transportation systems (ITS) have been the focus of researchers and scientists due to the critical role they play, in particular, road safety, and traffic scene monitoring. In fact, intelligent systems can perform many tasks such as traffic flow tracking, determining the speed of vehicles, and traffic signs management [1], [2]. Lately, semantic segmentation has become one of the most important tasks that have been highlighted, due to its importance in identifying objects and image understanding [3]. Figure 1 presents samples of traffic scene images from the CamVid dataset and their corresponding semantic segmentation. In fact, deep learning (DL) algorithms, especially convolutional neural network (CNN), were able to obtain very advanced results in traffic scene semantic segmentation, compared to traditional methods [4], [5]. Before, CNN were used only for tasks' identification and classification, but in the past few years, and they have been adapted to make semantic segmentation in several areas, such as magnetic resonance images (MRI) [6], satellite images [7], traffic scenes [8]. But the biggest barrier to real-time semantic segmentation is always the combination of high precision and low computational resources.

Figure 1. Samples from CamVid dataset [9]. The input images are at the bottom and their corresponding segmentation red green blue (RGB) masks are at the top

In the literature, diverse research papers on traffic scene semantic segmentation have been conducted. In Badrinarayanan *et al.* [10] proposed a new semantic segmentation encoder-decoder network named SegNet. The latter is based on VGG16, and it requires a large amount of parameters. According to [11], a deep CNN named ENet has been proposed. This network has satisfactory results in terms of parameter requirement; however, it does not have good accuracy. In [12], a new deep neural network called DeconvNet has been proposed. The DeconvNet uses 252M parameters, therefore, it requires a large computation cost, which makes it undesirable for real-time applications. To overcome the resource problem while keeping high accuracy, great efforts are needed to propose a new CNN model. In this regard, we propose a new residual and robust network called RBANet, and it is based on a new balanced attention module (BAM) and a new residual module. Our RBANet can gather between the parameters requirement and precision, which makes it practical for real-time applications. Our major contributions to this work are as: i) a new robust network for traffic scene semantic segmentation based on a new residual module, as well as a new BAM; ii) the proposed network achieved good results in terms of mean intersection over union (mIoU) and the required number of computational parameters.

The remainder of this paper is structured as. We will look at some research on traffic scene semantic segmentation in section 2. Then, in section 3, we explain the proposed network RBANet by giving details on the proposed residual module and the proposed BAM. Section 4 shows the experimental results on the CamVid dataset. Finally, the conclusion and future directions are presented in section 5.

2. RELATED WORK

This section addresses recent traffic scene semantic segmentation research work, such as real-time and offline segmentation. Real-time traffic scene semantic segmentation necessitates a model that combines speed and precision, which is a substantial and tough problem. Mehta *et al.* [13] proposed a new fast and efficient CNN for traffic scene semantic segmentation called ESPNet. The latter does not need great parameters' number; however, it does not attain excellent precision when compared to similar work. Subsequently Wu *et al.* [14] reconsider traffic scene semantic segmentation. As a consequence, they presented a novel context-guided block to learn the surrounding, local features, and context. This work achieves encouraging results. According to [15], a CNN inspired by the human brain called IkshanaNet, has been proposed. However, this network did not yield satisfactory results in terms of precision and parameter requirements. Later, the semantic segmentation neural network called EDANet has been suggested in [16]. The EDANet is structured and based on dense modules, which obtain impressive results. Thereafter, Li *et al.* [17] have introduced a novel model based on asymmetrical Depth-Wise Bottleneck named DABNet. The latter delivers good results in terms of precision, mIoU and parameters' requirements. According to [18], Visin *et al.* have developed a CNN named ReSeg based on VGG16 backbone. However, ReSeg did not produce satisfactory results in terms of precision, and the authors did not mention the number of parameters. Later, a new deep neural network based on feature aggregation called DFANet has been proposed in [19]. The latter achieved an acceptable result in terms of precision; however, the authors did not mention the parameters' number. Until now, all of the networks that have been designed are to achieve a compromise between inference speed and precision. However, further progress is required to improve precision while lowering resource costs.

Semantic segmentation tasks may be used in both online and offline applications. Offline segmentation is slow to process since it is indifferent to time. In this part, we will look at some recent work on offline traffic scene semantic segmentation. Chen *et al.* [20] have developed a CNN module using dilation to

improve the DeepLabv3 model. This adjustment made a significant difference in terms of precision, but it still has to be improved in terms of computation cost. After, a deep CNN model named BiSeNet has been proposed in [21], and it is based on the ResNet and Xception backbone. BiSeNet has achieved encouraging results in terms of precision, however, it is very expensive in terms of parameters' requirements, which is not suitable for real-time applications. In general, the models that are expensive in terms of computation resources may produce excellent gains in accuracy, however, the parameters constraint is usually the most difficult barrier. As a result, the heavy models are incompatible with various edge devices such as Raspberry Pi, Arduino, and field-programmable gate array (FPGA) [22].

3. METHOD

3.1. Dataset and metric

We have used CamVid, the most widely used traffic scene semantic segmentation dataset [9], which does not necessitate strong machine performance. Indeed, we have used the relevant work strategy to divide the entire image dataset into rain, test and validation sets that contain 367 images, 233 images, and 101 images respectively. In addition, there exist 32 classes, but only 11 of them are used for semantic segmentation in the CamVid dataset [23]. Furthermore, we provide our outcomes using the standard measure for semantic segmentation, mIoU, which is defined as (1) [24]:

$$\text{Mean IoU} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP+FN} \quad (1)$$

with TP , FP , and FN are the number of true pixel-level positives, false positives, and false negatives, and may have been computed for each semantic class.

3.2. Implementation setup

The PyTorch framework with CUDA backends is used for all experiments. Our proposed RBANet is trained from scratch, without pre-trained weight. We mention that we have used Adam [25] as an optimization algorithm, and we have chosen a learning rate of 0.045. We have used Google Collaboratory with Tesla K80 GPU and 12 GB RAM to train our proposed model. The outcomes of our simulation prove that the suggested network does not require a great parameters' number.

3.3. The proposed approach

3.3.1. Residual module

In this part, we will go through the proposed residual module in depth. Our proposed module is based on convolution factorization, which divides typical convolution layers into many stages to minimize processing time and memory expenses [26]. Therefore, this approach is frequently used in various lightweight CNN, such as ENet [11], EDANet [16], DABNet [17], ESNet [27], and LEDNet [28]. In this regard, we have created a novel residual module as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The proposed residual module

The proposed module contains 3×3 Conv layer, the latter is divided into two layers, in particular, 3×1 Conv, and 1×3 Dilated-Conv. After that, in the next level, we have linked the layer 3×1 Conv with another layer 3×1 Dilated-Conv, as well as we have linked the layer 1×3 Dilated-Conv to the layer 1×3 Conv. In parallel, and to get a larger field of view using fewer parameters, we applied dilated layers. Then, in an attempt to lower the computation cost, we have added a layer of 1×1 Conv. In addition, and in order to make our CNN stable and quicker, we have used batch normalization (BN) [29] with rectified linear unit (ReLU) [30] in each level of the convolution layer.

3.3.2. Balanced attention module

In this subsection, we will discuss the proposed balanced attention module (BAM), which discusses the potential of multi-layered attention convolutional blocks that are relayed in [31], [32]. The architecture of the proposed BAM involves the application of channel and spatial attention mechanisms to feature maps from preceding convolutional down sampler blocks using a balanced feature sharing mechanism. The channel attention block is used to extract useful information from the input image, while the spatial attention block further identifies the most useful information within the output received from the channel attention as illustrated in Figure 3(a).

In Figure 3(b), the channel attention module is depicted where the output features from preceding convolutional layers are refined. Firstly, the input features are max pooled and average pooled simultaneously. Average pooling is used to aggregate spatial information to induce a smoothing effect while max pooling is used to induce a sharpening effect by preserving contextual information in terms of object edges. The output features generated by the two pooling layers are simultaneously passed to the multi-layer perceptron (MLP) layers whose output vectors are then concatenated element-wise. The final resultant vector is then sent to the rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function, which generates the important feature maps for the spatial attention module.

In Figure 3(c), the spatial attention module is depicted where the output feature maps from the preceding channel attention module are further refined. Firstly, the input feature maps are max pooled and average pooled simultaneously for similar reasons as in the channel attention module. The output vectors from the pooling layers are then concatenated element-wise before being passed as input to a convolutional layer to produce a single channel feature map. Subsequently, the final feature map is sent to the ReLU function, which produces a spatial mask for the identification of important features. The spatial mask is applied to all significant feature maps from the preceding channel attention module to identify essential features by using element-wise multiplication. Finally, the output features from spatial attention are added with the input features using residual connections, to generate more refined and highlighted feature maps.

Figure 3. The proposed module (a) the overall BAM, (b) channel attention block, and (c) spatial attention block

3.3.2. The proposed RBANet

In this subsection, we will describe our intended architecture network, which is depicted in Table 1 and Figure 4. The RBANet is a robust network inspired by residual connections, which combine great accuracy with a limited amount of parameters [33]. As a result, it employs few convolutional layers with varying hyperparameters, therefore, it makes the proposed model lightweight. The proposed network is made up of five blocks, where the first one involves the initial stage. The second, third, and fourth blocks are composed of a downsampling Block, the proposed attention module, and the proposed residual module. The residual module is repeated four times in the second block with 16 input channels, and different dilation rates of $r=\{2, 2, 4, 4\}$. In the third block, the residual module is repeated four times with 64 input channels, and different dilation rates of $r=\{8, 8, 16, 16\}$. The fourth block consists of the same element mentioned for the precedent blocks, except that the residual module is repeated five times with 128 input channels, and different dilation rates of $r=\{32, 32, 64, 32, 32\}$. The fifth and sixth blocks use upsampling with the residual module repeated four times for each block. The fifth block uses 64 input channels and a dilation rate of $r=\{16, 16, 8, 8\}$, whereas, the sixth one uses 16 input channels, with a dilation rate of $r=\{4, 4, 2, 2\}$. Finally, we have used the ConvTranspose2d output convolutional layer.

Table 1. The detailed RBANet architecture

Stage	Block	Block Type	Number of Channels
Encoder	Block 1	Initial Block	16
		Downsampling Block	16
	Block 2	The proposed BAM	16
		The proposed Residual Module $\times 4(r=\{2, 2, 4, 4\})$	16
	Block 3	Downsampling Block	64
		The proposed BAM	64
		The proposed Residual Module $\times 4(r=\{8, 8, 16, 16\})$	64
		Downsampling Block	128
	Block 4	The proposed BAM	128
		The proposed Residual Module $\times 5(r=\{32, 32, 64, 32, 32\})$	128
Decoder	Block 5	Upsampling Block	64
		The proposed Residual Module $\times 4(r=\{16, 16, 8, 8\})$	64
	Block 6	Upsampling Block	16
		The proposed Residual Module $\times 4(r=\{4, 4, 2, 2\})$	16
		ConvTranspose2d	16

Figure 4. The overall architecture of the proposed RBANet

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We perform our RBANet on the CamVid dataset with a batch size of 8. During the training stage, we chose an image with a resolution of 360×480 as the relevant literature to keep the reliability. Furthermore, we have reached 66.82% in terms of mIoU using only 0.74M parameters, and 106 frames per second (fps), thus, we have outperformed many related work models. As we can see in Table 2, we have studied the proposed RBANet on the whole classes of the CamVid dataset. Afterward, we have made a careful study by experimenting three loss functions, in particular, Focal Loss [34], Cross-Entropy [35], and LovaszSoftmax [36]. To start, the LovaszSoftmax loss function has achieved 66.82% in terms of mIoU, and it has been eligible

to exceed the other loss functions in seven classes of the eleven, in particular, bicyclist, pedestrian, fence, sign symbol, pavement, pole, and building. Thus, we can say that our proposed RBANet using the LovaszSoftmax managed to obtain high precision in the most difficult and small classes. Afterward, with a mIoU of 65.64%, the cross-entropy loss function surpasses the other loss functions in three classes of the eleven, namely car, road, and sky. Moreover, the proposed RBANet using the cross-entropy has been able to get high precision in large classes, which are easy to recognize by the model. Finally, the Focal loss function achieves a mIoU of 64.58 % and surpasses the other loss functions in one class, which is Tree. In overall, the outcomes were nigh between all the loss functions.

Table 2. Detailed analysis of RBANet results on CamVid dataset using different loss functions

Loss functions	Sky	Building	Pole	Road	Pavement	Tree	Sign Symbol	Fence	Car	Pedestrian	Bicyclist	mIoU (%)
Cross Entropy	91.39	80.22	34.11	94.99	81.35	73.21	42.97	29.44	82.29	55.12	56.94	65.64
Focal	91.22	80.03	32.71	94.17	80.26	73.75	40.24	33.55	76.75	53.31	54.42	64.58
Lovasz Softmax	91.21	80.95	37.85	94.74	82.04	72.87	44.65	32.83	79.04	60.12	57.84	66.82

Table 3 compares several latest models on the CamVid traffic scene dataset. According to the reached results, our RBANet performs fluently in terms of mIoU, number of parameters and fps. Therefore, we observe that the proposed network is better suitable for practical uses and real-time applications than its competitors [14], [37]. Concerning the mIoU metric, we notice that our proposed RBANet outperforms the majority in the state of the art [17], [19], also there is a wide difference with some models [10], [12], [38]. In terms of the parameters' number, our RBANet outperformed the bulk of similar research as seen in Table 3. In addition, we can observe that some works with restricted parameters are inaccurate such as SegNet-Basic [10], and ENet [11], which makes them unsuitable for real-time applications. Furthermore, we discovered that the number of layers used in our proposed model has a direct relationship with the model weight size and fps. Despite the fact that most of the relevant work has not assessed these metrics, we have exceeded the majority of them, in particular, [16], [18], [39]. Besides that, whereas some models are formally pre-trained like, [10], [12], our RBANet is trained from scratch without using a pre-trained weight.

Table 3. Performance comparison of ELRNet with related work on CamVid test set

Models	mIoU (%)	Parameters (M)	Size (MB)	Fps	Pre-trained
SegNet [10]	55.6	29.5	56.2	-	Yes
FCN-8s [38]	57	134	-	39	Yes
DeconvNet [12]	48.9	252	-	26	Yes
SegNet-Basic [10]	46.3	1.4	-	70	No
DABNet [17]	66.4	0.84	-	117	No
DFANet [19]	64.7	-	-	120	No
ENet [11]	51.3	0.37	0.7	149	No
CGNet [14]	65.6	0.5	3.34	-	No
LMDNet [37]	63.5	-	66	34.4	No
Dilation8 [39]	65.3	140.8	-	-	No
EDANet [16]	66.4	0.68	-	-	No
ReSeg [18]	58.8	-	-	-	No
RBANet (our)	66.82	0.74	3.31	115	No

Figure 4 depicts a few test images using the proposed RBANet. Consequently, the outcomes prove that our proposed model can differentiate between distinct classes despite some little noise. Furthermore, we can observe that the predicted image output is clean and appears to be the ground truth. Considering all the achievements that are made in the related work, there are still issues in semantic segmentation of small classes such as tree, sign symbol, and pedestrian, as seen in Figure 5 and Table 3. As a result, it is vital to work on the segmentation of smaller classes in order to save the life of pedestrians and animals that may be damaged. On contrary, large classes such as road, car, and sky may be simply and precisely segmented.

Figure 5. RBANet evaluation result on CamVid dataset

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present a new robust and lightweight neural network called RBANet for real-time traffic scene semantic segmentation. Besides, we also propose a new attention module that uses spatial attention and channel attention. At the same time, we have proposed a new residual module. The proposed RBANet has been evaluated on the CamVid dataset, and this latter proves the segmentation rendering of the proposed model. In general, the RBANet displays a great improvement in terms of mIoU, and parameters' requirements compared to the state of the art. Our proposed model is trained from scratch, and it achieves a mIoU of 66.82% using only 0.74M parameters. The wide experiments demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed RBANet using different loss functions. Moreover, the parameters' requirement has been importantly relieved. In future work, we will mainly look forward to evolving new attention modules to reduce the computational cost, and improve precision.

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